

Low power circuit design using NCL based asynchronous method

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ABSTRACT

The null convention logic (NCL) based circuit design methodology eliminates the problems related to noise, clock tree, electromagnetic interference and also reduces significant power consumption. In this paper, we would like to demonstrate the advantage of low power consumption of the NCL based asynchronous circuit design on a large design scale, thus we used the advanced encryption standard (AES) encryption design as an illustrative example. In addition, we also proposed two pipelined AES encryption models using the synchronous circuit design technique and the asynchronous circuit design technique based on NCL. Besides, these two models were realized by using version control system (VCS) tool to simulate and Design Compiler tool to synthesize parameters in power consumption, processing speed and area. The synthesis results of these two models indicated that power consumption of the NCL based asynchronous AES encryption model had a decrease of 71% compared with the synchronous AES encryption model. Moreover, we show the outstanding advantage of the power consumption of the NCL based asynchronous design model (a decrease of 91.12% and 93.23%) compared to the synchronous design model using clock gating technique and without using clock gating technique respectively.

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1. INTRODUCTION

In recent decades, the digital world has still been dominated by the strong development of the synchronous circuit design techniques. However, as integrated circuits require the increase of the processing speed and the decrease of the feature sizes and of power consumption, synchronous circuits become difficult to respond because of the clock related issues such as clock skews, glitches, layout complexity for clock distribution networks and especially increase of power [1]. Power consumption could be also one of the major concerns in a lot of applications such as wireless, laptops, cell phones, movable medical devices because of staying their battery life time [2]. In recent years, there have been researches about low power integrated circuits using synchronous design techniques such as low power and high performance the fast fourier transform (FFT) with different radices [3], low power pseudo-random number generator [4], low power wakes up receiver based on ultrasound communication for wireless sensor network [5], low power implementation of a high throughput multi core advanced encryption standard (AES) encryption architecture [6]. Although all above mentioned studies had indicated an improvement

in power consumption, this power consumption is mainly due to the switching power remaining high as the clock frequency increases. Therefore, we would propose a new method, the null convention logic (NCL) based asynchronous circuit design method without clock, to make a decrease of power. The method has benefits of eliminating all the clock related issues listed above.

In the mid 1990s, Karl Fant and Scott Brandt firstly proposed NCL which is a delay insensitive logic and the type of asynchronous logic. NCL initially dedicated to designing application specific integrated circuit and very large scale integration circuits with lower power, lower noise, and lower electromagnetic interference [1]. Many studies from transistor level to gate level based on NCL have shown superior performance compared to studies based on traditional Boolean logic [7]-[11]. In addition, NCL is being studied for various purposes such as ultralow power high performance portable digital systems [12], bus alternatives for asynchronous circuits [13], AES encryption and decryption [14], low power designs [15]-[17]. D. L. Oliveira *et al.* [18], the authors indicated the outstanding advantage of low power of the NCL based asynchronous design. However, authors only implemented to examine for small designs such as threshold gates. On the other hand, in [19], 1 bit, 4 bit and 8 bit NCL ripple carry adders have been designed and compared with the corresponding ripple carry adders implemented using conventional synchronous complementary metal-oxide-semiconductor (CMOS) level design methodologies. The synthesis results in [19] indicated that NCL circuits have a significant decrease (about 65%) in power consumption. Both above mentioned models in [18, 19] were carried out on a small scale designs. Thus, in this paper, we would like to use a large scale design to demonstrate more clearly the low power advantage of the NCL based asynchronous design technique. We choose the AES encryption model as an example to implement because NCL has the advantage of securing cryptographic devices against side-channel attacks (SCA) and various power analysis attacks [20]. Although many authors have studied the AES algorithm [6], [14], [21], [22] by many various approaches, they have not shown advantages of the NCL based asynchronous design method compared with the other design method. In addition, we would like to propose two pipelined encryption models for the AES encryption using an asynchronous design method based on NCL and a synchronous design method. Both these AES encryption models are synthesized by design compiler tool with the same TSMC 65nm technology libraries. The comparison between these two methods in power consumption, area and processing speed is done. In addition, we also realize an extra comparison of the power between the NCL based asynchronous method and the synchronous design method using the clock gating technique and without using clock gating technique in [6] to prove some ideas why we choose the asynchronous design technique based on NCL for low power integrated circuit designs.

The rest of this paper is organized as follows: a description of the null convention logic and the general structure of the AES encryption algorithm are introduced briefly in section 2 and section 3. Then, section 4 and section 5 present respectively the proposed AES encryption models using the synchronous design method and the NCL based asynchronous design approach. Comparison between the two above mentioned methods and discussions are presented in section 6. The last section gives a conclusion of the proposed method.

2. NULL CONVENTION LOGIC (NCL)

NCL is a delay-insensitive paradigm used widely for designing asynchronous circuits in which the circuit will operate correctly regardless of the delay of the components and wires [9]. NCL circuits utilize dual-rail logic or quad-rail logic to achieve this purpose and NCL also uses two complete criteria which are the symbolic completeness of the expression and the completeness of the input [10]. A dual-rail signal, D is represented by 2 wires D0 and D1. The value of a dual-rail signal gets any value of the set {DATA0, DATA1, NULL} shown in the Table 1 [8]. Three logical states (NULL, DATA0 and DATA1) help dual-rail signals achieve the symbolic completeness of expression. The second criterion is the completeness of input showing that all outputs must not transit from null to data or data to null until all inputs have transited from null to data or data to null.

NCL uses a special type of gate, called a threshold gate, with hysteresis. There are 27 threshold gates with hysteresis in [9], [10] utilized in order to design NCL circuits. The general threshold gate is denoted as $Th_{mn}W_{n1}n_2$. Here, n is the total number of inputs, m is the threshold value that means at least m of the n inputs must be asserted before the output becomes asserted, and w is the weight of the inputs with values n_1, n_2 respectively. Figure 1 illustrates the primary threshold gate. Figures 2 and 3 are examples of an NCL dual-rail EXOR and 1 bit register, respective.

Table 1. Dual-rail signal

Boolean logic	Dual-rail logic	Code D1	Code D0
0	DATA0	0	1
1	DATA1	1	0
	NULL	0	0
	ILLEGAL	1	1

Figure 1. The primary threshold gate

Figure 2. NCL dual-rail EXOR

Figure 3. NCL dual-rail 1 bit register

3. THE AES ENCRYPTION FLOW

This section briefly presents 128-bit AES encryption (described in [21]) in which we use the key length of 128 bits. The flow of the AES encryption is implemented through five main function blocks: AddRoundKey, SubBytes, ShiftRows, MixColumns and KeyExpansion and they are arranged to perform through three basic steps shown in Figure 4. The implementation of the five functions mentioned above is presented and explained in detail in [14], [22].

- The first step is called as the initialization step in which the original plaintext is combined with the original key by the AddRoundKey transformation.
- The second step is named as the repeat encryption Step where the results from the first step are employed in order to sequentially perform functions such as SubBytes, ShiftRows, MixColumns and AddRoundKey. This step is also repeated nine times while the KeyExpansion transformation has to be performed in parallel with the AddRoundKey operation to create a key for this function.
- The final step is called as the output generation step where data output from the second step is executed through three sub-steps such as SubBytes, ShiftRows and AddRoundKey and the result of this step is ciphertext.

Figure 4. The AES encryption flow [23]

4. THE PROPOSED AES ENCRYPTION MODEL USING THE SYNCHRONOUS DESIGN METHOD

The synchronous AES encryption model illustrated in Figure 5 includes 11 rounds, 12 synchronous registers and a clock distributor pipelined by a twelve register system. Using an eleven-stage pipelined model also reduces the amount of logic in a clock cycle at the expense of more registers. That is the best way in order to reduce power consumption [24].

Figure 5. The synchronous AES encryption model

5. THE PROPOSED AES ENCRYPTION MODEL USING THE NCL BASED ASYNCHRONOUS DESIGN METHOD

The NCL based asynchronous AES encryption model is proposed and presented in this section. Figure 6 shows the asynchronous AES encryption model where the algorithm processes data blocks of 128 bits through the use of cipher keys with the lengths of 128 bits. Therefore, there are 11 rounds, 12 NCL registers and 11 completion detection circuits.

The K_o of the current register is connected to the K_i of the previous register and plays a role as an acknowledge and request signal. Initially, when reset signals in all NCL registers are turned on, the Null state is loaded into them, which causes K_o to transit from 0 to 1 state. Then Nulls are also loaded into computing blocks inside rounds, which causes signals in all rounds to Null. As a result, the circuit is on reset. When the output Q of a register returns complete Data, its K_o transits to 0 state and thus, drives K_i of the previous register to 0 state to wait for the Null wavefront [25]. Similarly, when the output Q of a register is already reset to a complete Null, its K_o will drive K_i of the previous register to 1 state to wait for the Data wavefront. Therefore, in an NCL system, two Data wavefronts will always be separated by the Null wavefront to avoid overwriting data. The structure of the initial round, round 1 to round 9, and the final round are shown in Figure 7, Figure 8, and Figure 9. In special cases, the first NCL register has no K_o signal because there is no round in front of it. The last NCL register has no next round so its K_o becomes K_i . A 128 bit NCL register comprising of 128 single bit NCL registers requires 128 completion signals. Since the maximum input threshold gate is the th_{44} gate, the number of logic levels in the completion component for a 128 bit register is given by $\log_4(128)=3,5$ [26] (approximately 4 levels) as shown in Figure 10. For the first register, it has no completion detection circuit depicted in Figure 11.

Figure 6. The asynchronous AES encryption model

Figure 7. The structure of initial round

Figure 8. The structure of round 1-9

Figure 9. The structure of final round

Figure 10. The structure of NCL 128 bits register and completion detection circuit

Figure 11. The structure of first NCL register

6. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The synchronous AES encryption model is simulated and synthesized for some parameters such as power consumption, processing speed and area by VCS tool and DC tool which use TSMC 65nm technology libraries. The simulation and synthesis results of the synchronous AES encryption model are depicted in Figure 12 and Figure 13. The maximum speed of the synchronous design model is shown in Figure 13 (c), where the maximum frequency is the frequency that the design still meets the timing. The function blocks in Figure 6 are also simulated and synthesized for the same parameters as in the synchronous AES encryption model by VCS, DC tool. In particularly, due to the lack of the NCL based asynchronous libraries, the synthesis results are also performed using the TSMC 65nm technology libraries shown in Figure 14.

```

Applications Places System Sat Jul 18, 8:50 AM albert
albert@localhost:~/aes/syn_aes/encryption
File Edit View Search Terminal Help
Time = 100, rst_n = 1, plaintext = 00112233445566778899aabbccddeeff, key = 00001111222233334444555566667777,
cipher = 1afbfbbc629898df1afbfbbc629898df
Time = 150, rst_n = 1, plaintext = 00112233445566778899aabbccddeeff, key = 00001111222233334444555566667777,
cipher = f692e687c690e4c315f185e425f387a0
Time = 200, rst_n = 1, plaintext = 00112233445566778899aabbccddeeff, key = 00001111222233334444555566667777,
cipher = 98be9227946bdec4873cd74439ea385
Time = 250, rst_n = 1, plaintext = 00112233445566778899aabbccddeeff, key = 00001111222233334444555566667777,
cipher = 56ab0b559889bfb2ccbeeeae4882d237
Time = 300, rst_n = 1, plaintext = 00112233445566778899aabbccddeeff, key = 00001111222233334444555566667777,
cipher = 5dd646f9a51da9a41b4fd579d69f44de
Time = 350, rst_n = 1, plaintext = 00112233445566778899aabbccddeeff, key = 00001111222233334444555566667777,
cipher = 92d9dc074188d9ea726d448a65792656
Time = 400, rst_n = 1, plaintext = 00112233445566778899aabbccddeeff, key = 00001111222233334444555566667777,
cipher = d29b8783db7caac6342f0c2f09efb28d
Time = 450, rst_n = 1, plaintext = 00112233445566778899aabbccddeeff, key = 00001111222233334444555566667777,
cipher = 71d5698272699561c7f7368fe80f6835
Time = 500, rst_n = 1, plaintext = 00112233445566778899aabbccddeeff, key = 00001111222233334444555566667777,
cipher = 66e94bd4ef8a2c3b884cfa59ca342b2e
Time = 550, rst_n = 1, plaintext = 00112233445566778899aabbccddeeff, key = 00001111222233334444555566667777,
cipher = 9c7373ae2c03c97f085291f55707e47b
$finish called from file "./testbench.v", line 53.
$finish at simulation time 20052
VCS Simulation Report
Time: 20052
CPU Time: 0.290 seconds; Data structure size: 0.1Mb
Sat Jul 18 08:50:03 2020
8:50:03 (snpslmd) IN: "VCSruntime_Net" albert@localhost.localdomain [snps_checkout_1595087403]
CPU time: .318 seconds in simulation
[albert@localhost encryption]$
    
```

Figure 12. The simulation result of the synchronous AES encryption model

Number of nets:	110987	Global Operating Voltage = 1.32
Number of cells:	87159	Power-specific unit information :
Number of combinational cells:	83933	Voltage Units = 1V
Number of sequential cells:	2966	Capacitance Units = 1.000000pf
Number of macros/black boxes:	0	Time Units = 1ns
Number of buf/inv:	11957	Dynamic Power Units = 1mW (derived from V,C,T units)
Number of references:	25	Leakage Power Units = 1pW
Combinational area:	218599.679843	
Buf/Inv area:	17254.080677	Cell Internal Power = 8.4162 mW (78%)
Noncombinational area:	35328.000000	Net Switching Power = 2.4173 mW (22%)
Macro/Black Box area:	0.000000	-----
Net Interconnect area:	undefined (No wire load specified)	Total Dynamic Power = 10.8335 mW (100%)
Total cell area:	253927.679843	Cell Leakage Power = 5.8524 uW

(a)

(b)

```

Timing Path Group 'clk'
-----
Levels of Logic:          17.00
Critical Path Length:    0.85
Critical Path Slack:     0.00
Critical Path Clk Period: 0.95
Total Negative Slack:    0.00
No. of Violating Paths:  0.00
Worst Hold Violation:   0.00
Total Hold Violation:   0.00
No. of Hold Violations: 0.00
-----

```

(c)

Figure 13. Extract reports on area, timing and power; (a) area report, (b) power report, and (c) timing report

Number of nets:	546823	Global Operating Voltage = 1.32
Number of cells:	269439	Power-specific unit information :
Number of combinational cells:	212782	Voltage Units = 1V
Number of sequential cells:	926	Capacitance Units = 1.000000pf
Number of macros/black boxes:	0	Time Units = 1ns
Number of buf/inv:	15164	Dynamic Power Units = 1mW (derived from V,C,T units)
Number of references:	23	Leakage Power Units = 1pW
Combinational area:	572166.720207	
Buf/Inv area:	22434.240800	Cell Internal Power = 2.4872 mW (81%)
Noncombinational area:	0.000000	Net Switching Power = 567.8337 uW (19%)
Macro/Black Box area:	0.000000	-----
Net Interconnect area:	undefined (No wire load specified)	Total Dynamic Power = 3.0550 mW (100%)
Total cell area:	572166.720207	Cell Leakage Power = 10.5392 uW

(a)

(b)

```

Timing Path Group (none)
-----
Levels of Logic:          43.00
Critical Path Length:    2.91
Critical Path Slack:     uninit
Critical Path Clk Period: n/a
Total Negative Slack:    0.00
No. of Violating Paths:  0.00
Worst Hold Violation:   0.00
Total Hold Violation:   0.00
No. of Hold Violations: 0.00
-----

```

(c)

Figure 14. Extract reports on area, power and timing; (a) area report, (b) power report, and (c) timing report

Because the synopsys DC tools do not support critical timing path for asynchronous designs, the maximum delay computation is based on the formula below [27]:

$$TDD = 2 * (T_{comb} + T_{comp}) = 5.82 \text{ (ns)}$$

using clock gating technique. Furthermore, compared to ultra low power encryption in [28], our work also shows a 27.60% improvement.

Figure 16. Power consumption for various frequencies

Table 3. Comparison of the power consumption of the methods

Specification	Area (μm^2)	Total Power (mW)	Speed (MHz)
NCL based Asynchronous design (our work)	572167	3.0653	171
Synchronous design with Clock Gating [6]		34.5277	667
Synchronous design without Clock Gating [6]		45.2924	667
Ultra low power Encryption [28]	211600	4.234	125

7. CONCLUSION

The NCL based asynchronous circuit design method not only has low power potential in small scale circuits but also has low power potential in large scale circuits. In this paper, we have demonstrated this potential through implementing two AES encryption models by using the synchronous circuit design technique and the NCL based asynchronous circuit design technique. Despite the lack of libraries and supporting tools, we recognize that the results of power consumption show the advantages of the NCL based asynchronous circuit design method over the synchronous circuit design method. If the power criterion of the integrated circuits is preferred, the NCL based asynchronous integrated circuit design method will be a promising candidate. Our future works will focus on analysis and synthesis of NCL based asynchronous circuits by using the dedicated libraries in order to validate convincingly low power property for the NCL based asynchronous circuit design method.

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